
Formulation And Evaluation of Domperidone Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets

Deepika Biswas^{1*}, Dr. Gaurav Bhaduka, Dr. Dilip Agrawal

^{1*}Research Scholar, Mahatma Gandhi College of Pharmaceutical Sciences, Jaipur, Rajasthan
Mail id: deepikabiswas001@gmail.com

Abstract: Pediatric, geriatric and bedridden patients have difficulties swallowing tablets. Domperidone (acting through D2 receptors) is an inhibitory transmitter in g.i.t. – normally acts to delay gastric emptying when food is present in stomach. It also appears to cause gastric dilatation and LES relaxation attending nausea and vomiting. Its prokinetic action is not blocked by atropine and is based only on D2 receptor blockade in upper g.i.t. It does act on CTZ, which is responsible for its antiemetic property. In the present study, rapidly disintegrating tablets of Domperidone were formulated by applying two methods. Sodium starch glycolate and treated agar used as superdisintegrants in mass extrusion technique and treated agar method respectively. Total eight formulations each group with four formulations. Tablets were evaluated for various parameters. The time taken for the in vitro disintegration, in vivo disintegration and in vitro dispersion were found in the range of 8 - 20 sec, 11 - 25 sec, and 17 - 32 sec respectively. All formulations showed good palatable mouth feel. The formulations F4 and F8 showed good release rates and found stable. Thus Domperidone rapidly disintegrating tablets can be prepared by using mass extrusion technique and treated agar.

Keywords: Domperidone, Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets, Superdisintegrants, Formulations, Gastric dilatation.

Introduction

Rapidly disintegrating tablets are solid unit dosage forms that placed in the mouth, allowed to disperse/dissolve in the saliva and then swallowed without the need for water. Rapidly disintegrating tablets are appreciated by a significant segment of the population, particularly pediatric, geriatric and bedridden patients, who have difficulty swallowing conventional tablets or capsules. Vomiting is the common problem during traveling and water availability chances are also less. Domperidone an antiemetic and prokinetic is a widely used drug in the treatment of vomiting /motion sickness. Its acceptable taste makes that drug as ideal drug candidate for the rapidly disintegrating tablets.

Recently pharmaceutical industry has become increasingly aware of the need that elderly be considered as a separate and unique medicare population. Though geriatric patients constitute a minor proportion of the population, its growth rate is high and hence will have significant impact on development of drug delivery systems. Thus mouth dissolving tablets are gaining more demand and popularity from last few years.

Mouth dissolving tablets are those when put on tongue, disintegrates instantaneously, releasing the drug, which dissolves or disperses in the saliva. The faster the drug into solution, the quicker the absorption and onset of clinical effect. Some drugs are absorbed from the mouth, pharynx and esophagus as the saliva passes down into the stomach. In such cases, bioavailability of drug is significantly greater than those observed from conventional tablet dosage form. The advantages of mouth dissolving dosage forms are increasingly being recognized in both, industry

and academics. Their growing importance was underlined recently when European Pharmacopoeia adopted the term “orodispersible tablet” as a tablet that to be placed in the mouth where it disperses rapidly before swallowing.

Methodology

In this present study, rapidly disintegrating tablets of Domperidone were prepared by using two methods: 1) Mass extrusion technique 2) Treated agar.

In mass extrusion formulations sodium starch glycolate, Eudragit E 100, Avicel PH 102, low substituted hydroxy propyl cellulose, lactose and in treated agar formulations mannitol, treated agar, lactose, aspartame was used as disintegrants and excipients. The following parameters were performed for evaluating the rapidly disintegrating tablets.

The prepared tablets were evaluated for angle of repose, bulk density, loose tapped density and also % Compressibility. Uncoated tablets were examined under a lens for the shape of the tablet and color was observed by keeping the tablets in light. Uniformity of thickness was performed by picking three tablets from each formulation randomly, measured individually by using dial-caliper (Mitutoyo, Japan) and expressed in mm. Hardness of the tablets were determined using Monsanto hardness tester and expressed in kg/cm². Friability of tablets was determined by using Roche friabilator and expressed in percentage (%).

Drug Content Uniformity

One tablet was weighed and powdered. The whole amount of powdered tablet was transferred into a 100 ml volumetric flask. Add 0.1N HCl up to the mark. After few minutes the solution was filtered; rejecting first few ml of the filtrate. 2ml of filtrate was taken in a 25 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with 0.1N HCl and analyzed spectrophotometrically at 283 nm.

Drug content in mg was calculated by using formula=

$$\frac{\text{Concentration in } \mu\text{g/ml} \times 100 \times 25}{2 \times 1000}$$

Ten tablets were selected randomly from each formulation and weighed individually to check for weight variation.

Wetting time and Water Absorption Ratio

A piece of tissue paper folded twice was placed in a small petridish (i.d. = 6.5 cm) containing 6 ml of distilled water, a tablet was put on the paper, and the time required for complete wetting was measured. The wetted tablet was then weighed. Three trials for each batch were performed and standard deviation was also determined. Yunxia Bi reported this method. Water absorption ratio, R, was determined using equation –

$$R = 10 \times \frac{W_a - W_b}{W_b}$$

Where, W_b = weight of the tablet before water absorption

W_a = weight of the tablet after water absorption

In vitro Dispersion Time

In vitro dispersion time was measured by dropping a tablet in a measuring cylinder containing 6 ml of pH 6.8 (simulated saliva fluid). Three tablets from each formulation were randomly selected and in vitro dispersion time was performed. Standard deviation was also determined and in vitro dispersion time is expressed in seconds.

In vitro Disintegration Test

Place one tablet in each of the 6 tubes of the basket. Add a disc to each tube and run the apparatus using pH 6.8 (simulated saliva fluid) maintained at $37.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$ as the immersion liquid. The assembly should be raised and lowered between 30 cycles per minute in the pH 6.8 maintained at $37.0 \pm 0.2^\circ\text{C}$. The time in seconds taken for complete disintegration of the tablet with no palpable mass remaining in the apparatus was measured and recorded.

In vitro Dissolution Studies

In vitro release studies were carried out using tablet dissolution test apparatus USP XXIII. Two objectives in the development of in vitro dissolution tests are to show (1) that the release of the drug from the tablet is as close as possible to 100% and (2) that the rate of drug release is uniform batch to batch and is the same as the release rate from those batches proven to be bioavailable and clinically effective.

The following procedure was employed throughout the study to determine the in vitro dissolution rate for all the formulations.

Dissolution medium	500 ml of 0.1N HCl
Temperature	37°C±1°C
RPM	50
Tablet taken	One tablet (Known drug content).
Volume withdrawn	1 ml every 3 minutes
Volume made up to	5 ml
λ_{\max}	283 nm
Beer's range	2-30 µg/ml
Dilution factor	5

The various parameters related to dissolution which are evaluated in the present work are as follows:

1. Drug release
2. Cumulative percentage drug release
3. Cumulative percentage drug retained
4. Model fitting of the release profiles using five different models viz. Zero order, First order, Higuchi matrix, Peppas model and Hixson-Crowell equation.

Stability Studies

Stability of a drug has been defined as the ability of a particular formulation, in a specific container, to remain within its physical, chemical, therapeutic and toxicological specifications.

The purpose of stability testing is to provide evidence on how the quality of a drug substance or drug product varies with time under the influence of a variety of environmental factors such as temperature, humidity and light, and enables recommended storage conditions, re-test periods and shelf lives to be established.

ICH specifies the length of study and storage conditions:

Long term testing 250C±20C /60% RH±5% for 12 months

Accelerated testing 400C±20C / 75% RH±5% for 6 months

In the present study, stability studies were carried out at 250C/60% RH and 400C /75% RH for a specific time period up to 30 days for selected formulations.

Results And Discussions

In this present study, rapidly disintegrating tablets of Domperidone prepared by two methods, total eight formulations were prepared in which formulations F1 to F4 by applying mass extrusion technique and formulations F5 to F8 using treated agar powder. The composition of eight formulations are given in Table 1.

Table 1: Composition of Rapidly Disintegrating Tablets of Domperidone

Ingredients (mgs)	Formulation code							
	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5	F6	F7	F8
Domperidone	10	10	10	10	10	10	10	10
Sodium starch glycolate	6	12	18	24	--	--	--	--
Avicel PH 102	102	98	93	88	--	--	--	--
Low hydroxy propyl cellulose	26	24	23	22	--	--	--	--
Eudragit E100	10	10	10	10	--	--	--	--
Treated Agar	--	--	--	--	10	20	30	40
Aspartame	--	--	--	--	10	10	10	10
Mannitol	--	--	--	--	124	114	104	94

Lactose	140	140	140	140	140	140	140	140
Magnesium stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	3	3	3	3	3	3	3	3

By I.R. study, it revealed that drug was compatible with all the formulation components. For each designed formulation, blend of drug and excipients was prepared and evaluated. Angle of repose was found in the range of 25.31' - 30.09', which indicates good flow. The loose bulk density and tapped bulk density for all the formulations varied from 0.56 gm/cm³ to 0.61gm/cm³ and 0.65 gm/cm³ to 0.72gm/cm³ respectively, which this results helps in calculating the % compressibility of the powder. The percent compressibility was in the range of 12.86 to 18.517 and results are shown in table no 2.

Table 2: Angle of Repose, Loose Bulk Density, Tapped Bulk Density, % Compressibility.

Formulation code	Angle of Repose (θ)	Loose Bulk Density(gm/cm ³)	Tapped Bulk Density (gm/cm ³)	% Compressibility
F1	28.82	0.59	0.72	18.52
F2	30.09	0.59	0.69	14.49
F3	29.56	0.57	0.66	13.64
F4	27.90	0.56	0.65	15.84
F5	28.29	0.59	0.69	14.49
F6	28.68	0.61	0.70	12.86
F7	27.65	0.59	0.71	16.90
F8	25.31	0.59	0.70	15.71

Tablets showed flat, circular shape in white color. The mass extrusion method (F1 to F4) tablets and treated agar (F5 to F8) tablets thickness was found in the range from 3.15 mm to 3.46mm and 2.66mm to 2.78 mm respectively. Hardness was found within 2.00 kg/cm² to 4.20 kg/cm², possessed good mechanical strength with sufficient hardness. Friability of the tablets was found well within the approved range (<1%) in all the formulation. All the tablets passed weight variation test as the % weight variation was within the pharmacopoeial limits of $\pm 7.5\%$ and found to be from 299.1 to 301.0mg. The drug content of all the formulated tablets were found between 9.525 ± 0.11 mg to 9.925 ± 0.068 mg of Domperidone.

In vitro Disintegration Time:

The internal structure of tablets, that is pore size distribution, water penetration into tablets and swelling of disintegration substance are suggested to be the mechanism of disintegration.

Table 3: Wetting Time, Water Absorption Ratio

Formulation Code	Wetting Time (n=3)	Water Absorption Ratio (n=3)
	Mean \pm SD	Mean \pm SD
F1	27.00 \pm 1.00	37.37 \pm 1.966
F2	23.67 \pm 0.58	33.89 \pm 1.343
F3	20.33 \pm 1.53	30.09 \pm 1.937
F4	15.33 \pm 1.53	29.08 \pm 1.406
F5	24.33 \pm 0.58	15.84 \pm 0.691
F6	22.67 \pm 0.57	19.45 \pm 2.144
F7	20.00 \pm 1.00	24.81 \pm 1.005
F8	17.00 \pm 0.00	29.89 \pm 1.626

The results are shown in Table No.3. This was determined as per I.P. for all the formulations. All formulations showed disintegration time less than 30 seconds. Formulation F4 & F8 showed fast disintegration compared to other formulation due to high concentration of disintegrates.

Table 4: In vitro Disintegration Time, In vitro Dispersion Time, In vivo Disintegration Time, Mouth Feel

Formulation Code	In vitro Disintegration Time	In vitro Dispersion Time	In vivo Disintegration Time	Mouth Feel
F1	19.67 ± 2.082	24.67 ± 1.16	32.00 ± 1.00	+
F2	17.33 ± 1.155	22.67 ± 0.58	28.00 ± 1.00	+
F3	13.00 ± 1.000	18.00 ± 1.0	24.33 ± 0.58	+
F4	08.30 ± 0.577	11.33 ± 1.16	18.00 ± 1.00	+
F5	14.33 ± 0.577	23.67 ± 1.16	28.67 ± 0.58	+
F6	14.33 ± 0.577	20.67 ± 0.58	26.33 ± 0.58	+
F7	12.67 ± 0.577	17.33 ± 0.58	21.67 ± 0.58	+
F8	10.33 ± 0.577	14.33 ± 1.16	17.67 ± 0.58	+

Wetting Time:

Wetting is closely related to inner structure of tablets. The record of the wetting time was shown in Table No.3. The wetting time in all the formulation were very fast. This may be due to ability of swelling and also capacity of absorption of water. L-HPC is having high water absorption capacity and cause swelling. Due to presence of pores in the treated agar, that absorbs water rapidly and swelling may lead. L-HPC and starch glycolate absorbs water rapidly in first four formulations (F1 to F4) and those formulations prepared with treated agar in F5 to F8, also absorbs the water rapidly and shows fast wetting time. This parameter also duplicates disintegration time in oral cavity as tablet is kept motionless on tongue, hence correlation between wetting time and disintegration time in oral cavity can also be made.

The water absorption ratio values of formulations F1 to F4 found in the range of 30.00 to 37.50 %, as L-HPC quantity decreases, the water absorption also decreases due to less swelling property. In the next four formulations F5 to F8, the results found in the range from 15.00 to 30.00%. The water uptake increased with an increased content of treated agar and caused a great deal of swelling.

In vitro dispersion time is measured by the time taken to undergo uniform dispersion. Rapid dispersion within seconds observed in all the formulations gives direct information regarding super-disintegrating nature of disintegrants used.

As the drug is not bitter and presence of Eudragit in F1, F2, F3 and F4, and Aspartame, Mannitol in F5, F6, F7, F8 showed good, palatable taste. All the formulations showed rapid disintegration in oral cavity, may be due to tablet porosity, hydrophilicity, swelling ability or pores of the disintegrants used. By observing the above results, sodium starch glycolate, L-HPC and Avicel PH 102 combination results in hydrophilicity and swelling which in turn causes rapid disintegration. The presence of pores in treated agar leads to rapid absorption of water and swelling that causes rapid disintegration. Thus these disintegrants are suitable in preparing the rapidly disintegrating tablets.

In vitro Dissolution Studies:

All the eight formulations were subjected for the in vitro dissolution studies using tablet dissolution tester USP XXIII. The samples were withdrawn at different time intervals and analyzed at 283nm. Cumulative drug release and cumulative % drug retained were calculated on the basis of mean amount of Domperidone present in the respective tablet.

The results obtained in the in vitro drug release for the formulations F1 to F4 are tabulated in Table No.5 and F5 to F8 in Table No.6.

Table 5: In vitro Dissolution Profile of the Formulations F1, F2, F3, F4

Formulation code	Time (min)	Absorbance at 283nm	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Conc. in 500ml(mg)	CLA (mg)	Cum. Drug Released (mg)	Cum. % Drug Released	Cum. % Drug Retained
F1	3	0.058	1.97	4.938	--	4.938	51.84	48.16
	6	0.071	2.40	6.000	0.009	6.009	63.08	36.92
	9	0.081	2.70	6.625	0.021	6.646	69.77	30.23
	12	0.092	3.12	7.800	0.034	7.834	82.25	17.75
	15	0.102	3.45	8.625	0.051	8.676	91.16	8.84
F2	3	0.059	2.00	5.000	--	5.000	52.63	47.37
	6	0.074	2.50	6.250	0.010	6.260	65.89	34.11
	9	0.084	2.85	7.125	0.023	7.148	75.24	24.76
	12	0.093	3.15	7.875	0.037	7.912	83.28	16.72
	15	0.104	3.52	8.800	0.053	8.853	93.19	6.81
F3	3	0.064	2.175	5.438	--	5.438	55.49	44.50
	6	0.078	2.650	6.625	0.011	6.636	67.72	32.28
	9	0.087	2.950	7.375	0.024	7.399	75.50	24.50
	12	0.102	3.450	8.625	0.038	8.664	88.42	11.58
	15	0.109	3.70	9.25	0.056	9.306	94.97	5.03
F4	3	0.078	2.650	6.625	--	6.625	67.60	32.4
	6	0.082	2.775	6.938	0.0132	6.951	70.93	29.07
	9	0.093	3.150	7.875	0.0271	7.902	80.64	19.37
	12	0.102	3.450	8.625	0.0428	8.668	88.45	11.55
	15	0.112	3.825	9.550	0.0603	9.610	98.07	1.93

Amount of drug present in one tablet. F1 = 9.525mg, F2 = 9.5mg, F3 = 9.799mg, F4 = 9.80mg

Table 6: In vitro Dissolution Profile of the Formulations F5, F6, F7, F8

Formulation code	Time (min)	Absorbance at 283nm	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Conc. in 500ml(mg)	CLA (mg)	Cum. Drug Released (mg)	Cum. % Drug Released
F5	3	0.064	2.175	5.438	--	5.438	56.13
	6	0.073	2.475	6.188	0.011	6.199	63.98
	9	0.086	2.900	7.250	0.023	7.273	75.07
	12	0.093	3.150	7.875	0.038	7.913	81.67
	15	0.105	3.550	8.875	0.044	8.919	92.05
F6	3	0.070	2.35	5.875	--	5.875	59.84
	6	0.081	2.70	6.625	0.012	6.637	67.60
	9	0.089	3.00	7.500	0.025	7.525	76.65
	12	0.102	3.45	8.625	0.040	8.665	88.26
	15	0.109	3.70	9.250	0.059	9.307	94.81
F7	3	0.073	2.475	6.190	--	6.186	62.48
	6	0.089	3.000	7.500	0.014	7.514	75.90
	9	0.095	3.225	8.060	0.029	8.089	81.71
	12	0.103	3.500	8.750	0.045	8.793	88.82
	15	0.114	3.875	9.688	0.064	9.752	98.50
F8	3	0.079	2.68	6.688	--	6.688	67.38

6	0.084	2.85	7.125	0.013	7.138	71.92
9	0.096	3.25	8.125	0.028	8.153	82.14
12	0.108	3.68	9.188	0.044	9.232	93.04
15	0.115	3.90	9.750	0.061	9.811	98.85

Amount of drug present in one tablet. F5 = 9.689mg, F6 = 9.818mg, F7 = 9.9mg, F8 = 9.925 mg

The cumulative percentage of Domperidone released as a function of time (t) for formulations F1 to F4 are shown in Fig No.1 and formulations F5 to F8 in Fig. No. 2.

Formulation F1, F2, F3, F5, F6 releases 91.16%, 93.19%, 94.97%, 92.05%, 94.81% respectively, at end of 15 minutes. The rapid drug dissolution was observed in F4, F7, F8 which releases 98.074%, 98.50% and 98.85% respectively at end of 15 minutes. This rapid dissolution might be due to fast breakdown of particles and rapid absorption of drug. Because the drug, Eudragit (in mass extrusion technique) and Mannitol (in treated agar method) are showing high solubility in dissolution medium. The drug release was completely achieved in a shorter duration of time. In all the formulations the drug release was nearer to 100% within 15 minutes. High dissolution may also be due to faster breakdown. F1, F2, F3, F5 and F6 showed release variation probably due to slow breakdown of particles.

Cumulative % drug retained as a function of time were calculated for formulations F1 to F4 shown in Table No.7 and F5 to F8 in Table no.8, and graphical representation is shown in Fig. No.3 and Fig No.4 respectively.

Table 7: In vitro Dissolution Profile of the Formulations F1, F2, F3, F4

Formulation code	Time (min)	Absorbance at 283nm	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Conc. in 500ml(mg)	CLA (mg)	Cum. Drug Released (mg)	Cum. % Drug Released	Cum. % Drug Retained
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	9	0.093	3.150	7.875	0.0271	7.902	80.64	19.37
	12	0.102	3.450	8.625	0.0428	8.668	88.45	11.55
	15	0.112	3.825	9.550	0.0603	9.610	98.07	1.93

Amount of drug present in one tablet. F1 = 9.525mg, F2 = 9.5mg, F3 = 9.799mg, F4 = 9.80mg

Table 8: In vitro Dissolution Profile of the Formulations F5, F6, F7, F8

Formulation code	Time (min)	Absorbance at 283nm	Conc. in $\mu\text{g/ml}$	Conc. in 500ml(mg)	CLA (mg)	Cum. Drug Released (mg)	Cum. % Drug Released
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respectively at end of 15 minutes. High dissolution may also due to faster breakdown and rapid absorption of drug. Eudragit (in mass extrusion technique) and Mannitol (in treated agar method) are showing high solubility in dissolution medium. The drug release was completely achieved in a shorter duration of time.

To know the order of release the release rates were subjected to kinetic treatment for two modes: 1) Cumulative percent drug released Vs. Time 2) Log cumulative percent drug retained Vs. Time.

The correlation coefficient and slope values obtained are found linear for first order release. Next, the model fitting of the release profiles were performed using PCP DISSO-V2 software to observe the mechanism and correlation coefficient values obtained for all five models. The formulations F4 and F8 shows First order may be due to rapid diffusion or the porous nature and other formulations follows Peppas model due to diffusion co-efficient in which the release of drug occurs by diffusion following Fickian transport mechanism.

The formulations F4, F7, F8 were selected for stability studies on the basis of their high cumulative % drug release and also results of in vitro disintegration time, wetting time, in vivo disintegration time and in vitro dispersion time studies. The stability studies were carried out at 25°C/60% RH and 40°C/75% RH for all the selected formulations up to 30 days. The tablets were analyzed for hardness, friability, in vitro disintegration, drug content and wetting time. The results showed no significant variations in the above said parameters and were found stable.

References

- [1]. Abdelbary G, Prinderre P, Couani C, Taochim J, Reynier JP, Piccerelle P. The preparation of orally disintegrating tablets using a hydrophilic waxy binder. *Int J Pharm* 2004; 278(2) : 423-33.
- [2]. Martindale. The Complete Drug Reference, The Royal Pharmaceutical Society, London, 32nd edn; 1999.
- [3]. British Pharmacopoeia. The Department of Health Social Services and Public Safety. The Stationary Office Ltd., London, Volume I, 2001.
- [4]. Ramana RG, Rojagopala KG, Avadhanulu AB, Vatsa DK. Spectrophotometric estimation of Acebutolol hydrochloride and Domperidone in their dosage forms. *The Eastern Pharmacist* 1990 May; 133-135.
- [5]. Watanabe A, Hanawa T, Sugihara M. New oral dosage for the elderly; rapidly dissolving tablet in mouth without the addition of water. *J Pharm Sci Technol* 1994; 54 : 103-110.
- [6]. Reddy L.H., Ghosh B. and Rajneesh. Fast dissolving drug delivery system; A review of the literature. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2002; 64(4): 331-336.
- [7]. Martindale. The Complete Drug Reference, The Royal Pharmaceutical Society, Kanthleen Parfitt (Ed), Pharmaceutical press, Massachusetts, 32nd edn; 1999, 1190.
- [8]. Ishikawa T, Watanabe Y, Utoguchi N, Matsumoto M. Preparation and evaluation of tablets rapidly disintegrating in saliva containing bitter taste-masked granules by the compression method. *Chem Pharm Bull* 1997; 47(10) : 1451-1454.
- [9]. Akihiko I, Masayasu S. Development of oral dosage form for elderly patients; use of agar base of rapidly disintegrating oral tablets. *Chem Pharm Bull* 1996; 44(11): 2132-2136.
- [10]. Subramanyam CVS. Textbook of Physical Pharmaceutics, Vallabh Prakashan, 2nd edn; 2001.
- [11]. Yunxia B, Hisakazu S, Yorinobu Y, Kazumi D, Akinobu O, Kotaro I. Preparation and evaluation of compressed tablet rapidly disintegrating in the oral cavity. *Chem Pharm Bull* 1996; 44(11) : 2121-2127.
- [12]. Redkar MR, Gore SP, Devarajan PV. D-Zolv taste masked mouth dissolve tablets. *Indian J Pharm Sci* 2002; 64(3) : 291-292.

